

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17737314

Assessment Of Performance Of Hybrid Pigs Fed Diets Supplemented With Processed Cassava Peels In Awka North L.G.A In The Rainforest Zone Of Nigeria

¹Mefoh, N.C., ¹Ezechi, C.U. & ²Ikeogu C.

¹Anambra State Polytechnic, Mgbakwu, Nigeria

²Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Corresponding author: Mefoh N.C

ABSTRACT

Nine growing pigs with an average initial weight of 18.4 ± 6.5 kg were randomly assigned to three treatment diets in a completely randomized design. Each treatment diet had three replicates. The diets were diet A (control having no cassava peels substituting maize); diet B having 15% of maize substituted with cassava and diet C having 30% of the maize substituted with cassava peels. The pigs were fed to satiation twice daily. The growth performance and feed utilization indices of the pigs fed the treatment rations were assessed using total body weight gain (TBWG), mean fortnightly increase in weight (FBWG), specific growth rate (SGR) and food conversion ratio (FCR). Pigs fed diet B with 15% of maize replaced by cassava peels, exhibited the best TBWG of 17.50 ± 2.65 kg above that of control diet A (14.83 ± 2.05 kg) and diet C (11.83 ± 2.51 kg); best SGR (0.0084 ± 0.0059) above diet A (0.0072 ± 0.0063) and diet C (0.0064 ± 0.0047) and FCR (13.52 ± 12.35) better than the control diet A (18.40 ± 17.88) and diet C (19.28 ± 23.96). The analysis for feed cost per kilogram weight gain of the pigs fed the different diets showed that pigs fed diet B (N4038.68 ± 3676.8/kg weight gain) exhibited the best economic advantage above diet C (N5498.97 ± 6834.58/kg) and diet A (6230.38 ± 6028.53/kg). The results were however not significantly different at $p = 0.05$. It can thus be concluded that moderate replacement of maize with cassava peels in the diet of growing pigs would not be deleterious or detrimental to the pig's growth but would have economic benefits converting agro waste into wealth.

Keywords: Growing pigs, diet, cassava peels, maize, growth performance.

INTRODUCTION

Pig production can mitigate the animal protein shortage in Africa due to the animals' fast growth, short generation interval, high prolificacy, efficient nutrient conversion into high quality meat and ability to convert agro-waste into nutritious meat (Adesehinwa *et al.*, 1998). Pig performance in terms of weight and efficiency of gain and carcass leanness is related to the intake levels and therefore intake of particular nutrients, particularly energy and protein. However, feedstuffs and ingredients used in pig ration formation such as maize, soyabean meal, groundnut cake, etc, have continued to be scarce and costly due mainly to their low production and competition as food by humans in Nigeria. Commercial pig production employs concentrate feeds (maize and soyabean based), whose cost is increasing due to poor local production that fails to meet demand for consumption by people and other uses (Afolayan, 2010). This has caused the collapse of many small and large scale pig enterprises, discouraging prospective farmers and curtailing further expansion of small scale backyard piggeries (Ekwe *et al.*, 2011). Limited feed supply and poor quality of the available feed are the major constraints for optimal livestock

productivity in the tropical and subtropical countries (Bounfennara *et al.*, 2012). It is therefore necessary to explore other non conventional feedstuff that can be used in formulating pig rations to substitute for expensive conventional feed ingredients. There is a need to find ways to utilize available agro-industrial waste in the formulation of pig diets, in order to reduce the cost of meat production (Williams, *et al.*, 2023). The potential of many industrial by-products such as cassava peels, palm kernel meal, brewers spent grains, wheat offals, etc., to serve as alternative, cheaper and readily available nutrient source for pigs has been recognised but not fully utilized (Nwakpu *et al.*, 1999). With rising cost of feed ingredients and the increased capital and foreign exchange rates, farmers and feed manufacturers are changing their operations towards greater reliance on locally available feedstuffs (Brattle *et al.*, 2012).

Maize is one of the staple food crops for human beings particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and a major staple in swine diet in many areas of the world {FAOSTAT, 2015 in Fatufe *et al.*, 2017). In Nigeria, maize constitute up to 40 - 60% of the conventional energy source for poultry feeding (Afolayan *et al.*, 2012). The low level of maize production in the country has resulted in a situation such that greater percentage of the maize used in the country are imported and the competition between man and animals in terms of consumption and other uses has led to substantial increase in the price of maize (Fatufe *et al.*, 2017). In order to sustain pig production, therefore, there is need to provide alternatives to maize as the major energy source for pig. Cassava peel, a residue of cassava (*Manihot esculenta sp.*) root(tuber) processing, is a valuable feedstuff in pig nutrition in the tropics that helps small and medium scale pig farmers to reduce their feeding costs(Akinola *et al.*, 2013). Various studies reported it's possible utilization for replacement of maize and its better use by pigs when processed by fermentation or sun drying (Adesehinwa *et al.*, 2008). Major hindrances to high level inclusion of cassava peels in pig diets are its low crude protein content, poor amino acid profile, comparatively high fibre concentration, high concentration of free cyanide and low energy value (Salami and Odunsi, 2003). Cyanide problem can be overcome effectively by simple and cheap sundrying (Chauynarong *et al.*, 2009) or fermentation and sundrying, leaving high fibre content and low digestibility as its major drawback. Sundrying has been reported by Cardoso *et al.*, 2005 and Nguyen *et al.*, 2012, to eliminate almost 90% of nutritionally active deleterious factors. Lowered dietary crude protein concentration, when balanced by a supply of free amino acids (FAA), has been reported to be accompanied by less losses of energy via urine and heat production and an increased energy retention in pigs(Le Bellego *et al.*,2001).

With increased realization of the potentials of pig as quick source of animal protein and revenue/income generation with attributes such as: high litter size, short generation interval, high growth rate, high profligacy, ability to convert kitchen waste into nutritious meat(Ekwe, *et al.*, 2011).there is every need to find ways of utilizing some of the domestic waste like cassava peels in formulating pig/swine diets(Smith *et al.*, 2000, Ekwe *et al.*, 2011)

This study was therefore conducted to assess the growth performance and nutrient utilization of weaner pigs fed diets containing dried cassava peels and whole maize in various proportions.

Materials and methods.

Study site: The study was conducted at the piggery unit of Anambra State Polythecnic, Mgbakwu, Awka North, Anambra State. The site has a standard piggery house with open sides covered with nets, concrete floor and roofed with aluminum sheets. Each of the pens measuring 2.4m x 3.4m had feeding and watering arrangements.

Experimental animals: Nine grower pigs weighing averagely 18.41kg were used for the study. They were allotted into three treatment groups with three replicates in a completely randomized design. The animals were dewormed a week before feeding trials began.

Cassava Peels: Cassava peels used were collected from a cassava processing plant at Mgbakwu, soaked for four days and sundried for two days before milling/grinding. Other feed ingredients were bought from Afor Nnobi market in Idemili South L.G.A of Anambra State.

Experimental diets: Three experimental diets were formulated using mixes with whole maize and sundried cassava peel meal in various proportions. The diets were designated diets A, B and C. Diet A (control) had corn/maize (and other feed ingredients) without replacement with cassava peel meal, while

Diet B had 15,% of the corn substituted with cassava peel and diet C had 30% of the corn substituted with cassava peel meal. The ingredients composition of the diets is shown in table 1. Table 1. Composition of test diet.

S/N	Feed Ingredients.	Diets.		
		A.(kg)	B.(kg)	C.(kg)
1.	Corn.	30.95	26.31	21.67
2.	Cassava.	-----	4.64	9.28
3.	Brewer's dried grains.	29.1	29.1	29.1
4.	Fishmeal.	1.0	1.0	1.0
5.	Soyabean.	6.15	6.15	6.15
6.	Palm kernel cake.	28.8	28.8	28.8
7.	Vitamin-mineral premix.	0.5	0.5	0.5
8.	Lysine.	0.25.	0.25.	0.25.
9.	Methionine.	0.25.	0.25.	0.25.
10.	Bone.	2.0.	2.0.	2.0.
12.	Salt.	1.0.	1.0.	1.0
	Total.	100.0.	100.0.	100.0.

Feeding and collection of Data: The pigs were weighed at the beginning of the experiment to obtain their initial live weight and subsequently weighed every two weeks. They were fed to satiation twice daily in the morning (between 7 and 9 am) and in the evening (between 4 and 6pm). The parameters assessed included live weight, biweekly weight gain, feed intake, specific growth rate and food conversion ratio. The cost of the experimental diets was calculated per kilogram of dry feed. The feeding trials lasted for twelve(12) weeks.

Growth Performance and Feed Utilization indices:

Indices for growth performance and feed utilization were computed as given below.

Total body weight gain = final body weight - initial body weight.

Percentage total body weight gain = (final body weight - initial body weight)/ initial body weight x 100%

Specific growth rate (SGR) = (In Wf - In Wi)/T. where Wf =final mean weight; Wi = initial mean weight; In = Natural logarithm; T = time in days.

Food conversion ratio (FCR) = feed intake/ wet weight gain.

Feed cost/weight gain = (feed intake x unit cost of feed)/weight gain.

Statistical analysis: Data obtained were subjected to a one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the means separated using Duncan's multiple range test.

Results and discussion: The results for growth performance of grower pigs fed diets with different proportions of dried cassava peel meal substituted for whole maize meal is shown in table 2.

Table 2. Growth and feed utilization indices/parameters

Parameter/Indices.	Diets.			SEM.	P-value
	A.	B.	C.		
1. IBW	19.4+_ 7.43.	16.5+_ 4.97.	19.33+_ 6.47	2.17.	NS.
2. FBW.	34.23+_11.06.	34.00+_ 2.83.	31.17+_ 5.39.	2.47.	NS.
3. FBWG	2.47+_ 2.05	2.92+_ 2.03.	1.97+_ 1.10	0.22.	NS
4.%FBWG	11.07+_10.93	14.07+_ 11.38	9.54+_ 7.54	1.42.	NS.
5. TBWG.	14.83+_ 2.05.	17.50+_ 2.65.	11.83+_ 2.51.	1.30.	NS.
6. %TBWG.	84.89+_31.26	94.25+_ 31.60.	75.28+_42.81.	11.63.	NS.
7. SGR	0.0072+_ 0.0063	0.0084+_0.0059	0.0064+_ 0.0047	0.0008.	NS
8. FCR.	18.40+_17.88.	13.52+_12.35.	19.28+_23.96.	2.82.	NS.
9. FC/WG.	6230.4+_6028.5.	4038.7+_3676.8.	5498.97+_6834.6.	855.6.	NS.

Notes: IBW - Initial body weight; FBW - Final body weight; FBWG - Fortnightly body weight gain; TBWG - Total body weight gain; % - percentage; SGR - Specific growth rate; FCR - Food conversion ratio; FC/WG - Feed cost(Naira) per kilogram weight gain.

DISCUSSION

The mean fortnightly weight gain of pigs fed the various diets had diet B with 15% of corn substituted with dried cassava peels and accounting for 4.64% of total diet content having the highest value of 2.92+-2.03kg followed by control diet A(2.47+-2.05kg) with no dried cassava peel meal. The least value(1.97+-1.10kg) was shown by diet C having 30% replacement of whole corn with dried cassava peels. Although the final mean weight of pigs fed diet A (34.23kg) was highest for pigs fed the various diets, above those of diet B (34.00kg) and diet C (31.17kg), this could be as a result of differences in the initial mean weights of the pigs. The trend for specific growth rate (SGR) shows pigs fed diet B having the best specific growth rate of 0.0084+-0.0059 followed by pigs fed control diet A(0.0072+-0.0063), while pigs fed diet C had the poorest specific growth of 0.0064+- 0.0047.

Pigs fed diet B had the lowest value for food conversion ratio(FCR) of 13.52+- 12.35, signifying a better FCR compared to control diet A(18.40+-17.88) with diet C showing the poorest FCR (19.28+-23.96). The metrics for total body weight gain (TBWG), percentage total body weight gain (% TBWG), mean fortnightly body weight gain(FBWG) all showed pigs fed with diet B exhibited better growth performance compared to pigs fed the control diet A and diet C. The feed cost per weight gain (FC/WG) for diet B was also the best of the diets showing the least FC/WG of #4038.68+-3676.77/kg weight gain which was better than that of diet A(6230.38+-6028.53) and diet C (5498.97+-6834.58). The results however were not significantly different at 5% level of significance, ie $p = 0.05$

Increasing the quantity of dried cassava peels used in the diets of animals, pigs included, increases the fibre content of the diet as observed by Ekwe *et al.*, 2011, Coffey *et al.*(1982) in Ekwe *et al.*, 2011 suggested that increased fibre content of diet depressed growth rate in pigs especially during periods of high temperature which is prevalent in the tropics. Fibrousness, has also been reported by Longe and Fagbenro-Byron(1990) as a feature of most locally available agro-industrial by-products and waste that limit their use. Again the physical bulk associated with high fibre content of diets may affect the overall retention time of digestion in the gastro-intestinal tract and consequently, their utilization(Eruvbetine,1995).Akinola *et al.* (2013) reported that digestibility of dry matter(DM), organic matter(OM) and crude protein (CP) decreased with increasing replacement of maize by cassava root peel (CRP). They also noted a decrease in digestible energy with increased inclusion of CRP, this being caused by the increasing fibre concentration and the low digestibility of CRP fibre. Substituting large quantities of whole maize/corn with cassavs could also result in lowered energy value of the diet due to the differences in energy value of corn and cassava peels. This could impact energy available in the diets for tissue formation and growth. Modest substitution of cassava (15%) for corn in diet may not have increased the fibre content of the diet to a point where it will reduce the efficiency of the diet for growth while at the same time ensuring that there is not much reduction in the energy value of the diet.

While this study partly agrees with Akinola *et al.*(2013), who opined that cassava root peel could be used to replace up to 40% of maize in the diet of grower pigs, the results of this study shows that it will be better to replace maize with cassava root peels at a slightly lower percentage at about 15% to 20% as pigs fed diet with cassava root peels replacing 15% of corn gave the best growth and feed utilization indices. Akinola *et al.*(2013), agree that higher percentage inclusions (above 40% replacement of corn) of cassava root peels in pig diet will have negative effects on the growth of pigs. Fatufe *et al.* (2017), reported that nutrient digestibility of growing pigs could still be maintained with up to 30% inclusion of high quality cassava peel (HQCP) in the diet, but this study indicates that lower inclusion levels may be better.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the growth metrics for the treatment diets that dried cassava peel can be used moderately to replace up to 15% of corn in pig diet with advantageous growth and economic returns.

Replacing corn with cassava peels in higher amounts though supporting growth might not be economical for the pig farmer as shown by the results in this study with diet C showing the poorest performances for all the growth and feed utilization indices although its feed cost per weight gain was slightly better than that of the control diet. It is recommended that the pig farmer replace maize with cassava peels at moderate rates to confer economic advantage to the farmer while converting agro-waste to wealth in that way.

REFERENCES

- Adesehinwa, A.O.K., Dafwang, I.I., Ogunmodede, B.K. and Tegbe, T.S.B.(1998). A review of utilization of some agro-industrial by products in pig rations. *Nigerian Journal of Agricultural Extension*.11(1&2): 50 - 54.
- Adesehinwa, A.O.K., Dairo F.A.S. and Olagbegi B.S.(2008). Response of growing pigs to cassava peel based diets supplemented with avizyme (R) 1300; growth, serum and haematological indices. *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science*. 14:491 - 499.
- Afolayan, S.B., Dafwang I.I., Tegbe T.S.B and Sekoni A.(2012). Response of Broiler chicken fed on maize - based diets substituted with graded level of Sweet Potato meal. *Asian Journal of Poultry Science*. 6(1):15 - 22.
- Akinola S.O., Fanimio A.O., Ogunbiade J.A., Susenbeth A. and Schlecht E.(2013). Cassava root peel as a replacement for maize in diets for growing pigs: effects on energy and nutrient digestibility, performance and carcass characteristics. *Journal of Agriculture and Rural Development in the tropics and subtropics*. Vol 14, No 2: 159 - 166.
- Brattle L., Amata I.A., Omeje S.I. and Egbunike G.N.(2012). The effects of partial replacement of dietary maize with seeds of African pear (*Dacryode edulis* G.Don, H.J. Lana) on semen characteristics of broiler breeder cocks. *Asian Journal of Animal Science*. 5: 71 - 79.
- Bounfennara, S., Lopez S., Bodas R. and Bouaza L.(2012). Chemical composition and digestibility of some house plants collected from Algerian rangelands. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Resources* 10: 188 - 199
- Cardoso A.P., Estevao M., Mario E., Fernando M., Julie C., Hague M.R. and Bradbury J.H. (2005). Processing of cassava roots to remove cyanogens. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*.18: 451 - 460. DOI:10.1016/j.jfca.2004.04.002.
- Chauynarong N., Elangovan A.V. and Iji P.A.(2009). The potential of cassava products in diet for poultry. *World Poultry Science Journal*.65:26 - 35.
- Coffey M.T., Seerly R.W., Funderburke D.W. and Campbell H.C.(1982). Effect of heat increment and level of dietary energy and environmental temperature on the performance of growing - finishing swine. *Journal of Animal Science*. 54:95 - 105.
- Ekwe O.O., Nweze B.O. and Uchewa E.N.(2011). Effects of sundried cassava peels supplementation on the performance of weaner pigs. *Asian Journal of Applied Sciences*. 4(8): 794 - 800.
- Eruvbetine D. (1995). Processing and utilization of cassava as animal feed for non-ruminant animals. Paper presented at the workshop on alternative feedstuff for livestock Organized the Lagos State Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperative and Rural Development, Lagos, Nigeria. In: Ekwe O.O., Nweze B.O. and Uchenna E.N. (2011). Effects of sundried cassava peels supplementation on the performance of weaner pigs. *Asian Journal of Applied Sciences*.4(8):794 - 800.
- Fatufe A.A., Adebiyi O.A., Adesehinwa A.O.K., Ajayi E., Abidoye R.K., Samireddypalle A. and Afolabi O.O.(2017). High quality cassava peel fine mash as replacement for maize in diets of growing pigs:2. Effects on nutrient and fibre fraction digestibility. *Nigerian Journal of Animal production* 4(4):190 - 197.
- Le Bellego L.,u van Milgen J., Dubois S. and Noblet J.(2001). Energy utilization of low protein diets in growing pigs. *Journal of Animal Science*. 79:1259 - 1271.

- Nwakpu P.E., Omeje S.S.I and Odo B.I.(1999). Performance of weaner pigs fed diets containing different proportions of derived cassava peel and whole maize. *Tropical Journal of Animal Science*. 2:81 - 87.
- Nguyen T.H.L., Verstegen M.W.A. and Hendricks W.H.(2012). Ileal and total tract apparent crude protein and Amino acid digestibility of ensiled and dried cassava leaves and sweet potato Vines in growing pigs. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*. 172: 171 - 179. DOI: 10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2011.009.
- Salami R.I. and Odunsi A.A. (2003). Evaluation of processed cassava root peels as substitute for maize in the diet of layers. *International Journal of Poultry Science*.2:112 - 116.
- Williams G.A., Akinola O.S., Adeleye T.M., Irekhore O.T., Oso A.O., Ogunrombi J.O. and Williams O.K.(2023). Dietary replacement of maize with processed cassava peel leaf blends: impact on the growth performance and blood parameters of growing pigs. *Animal Science and Genetics*. 19(1):39 - 54. DOI: 10.5604/01.300/.0016.3140.